

GS/S/E/F92
(3a-d)
(CE8)

SHERD SHEET

MATCH WITH OTHER CORPORA

CORPUS	WARE DESIGNATION	TYPE DESIGNATION

I. TECHNIQUE

A. HAND MADE	1. Hand Modelled	2. Coiling	3. Plate Building
	4. Core Moulding	5. Turntable (up. pt.)	6. Other
B. TURNTABLE	?	C. WHEELMADE	?
E. CASTING			

II. FABRIC

A. TEXTURE OF CLAY

GENERAL:	Coarse	Medium X	Fine
1. Pebble	2. Granule	3. Very Coarse	4. Coarse
5. Medium	6. Fine	7. Very Fine	8. Silt

B. COMPOSITION Type of Clay: NILE ALLUVIAL

TEMPER (General):	Heavy X	Medium	Light
1. Material	SAND	Chuff Bunt out	
2. Particle Size	4 / mm		

C. FRACTURE COLOR

General Description	Munsell
Grey to Red Brown at walls	

D. HARDNESS VERY HARD

E. POROSITY

F. TRANSVERSE STRENGTH

G. PERMEABILITY

III. SURFACE PROPERTIES

A. SURFACE TREATMENT

1. Untreated	2. Wheel Finish	?	a. ribbing	?
			b. scrapped or shaved	
3. Hand Finish	a. smoothed	X	b. polished by burnishing	c. polished by rubbing
	d. scrapped		e. scratched or combed	f. other
4. Coating	a. wash		b. slip	c. glaze

B. SURFACE TEXTURE Grainy

C. MECHANICAL CONDITION OF SURFACE

Shallow low relief "ribbs" for length of preserved vessel - phasing shallower to what has been considered top of vessel (3d). Over the undulations of this ->

D. LUSTER

1. Matte	X	2. Low	3. Medium	4. High
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E. SURFACE COLOR

General Description	CEC	Munsell
RED BROWN		E11 to D11

IV. DECORATION

A. TECHNIQUE

1. Incised	2. Impressed	3. Gouged	4. Pinched
5. Modelled	6. Moulded	7. Painted	8. Inlaid

ribbing, very fine horizontal striations throughout outer wall of vessel. Interior: More pronounced undulations (ribbing?) and more pronounced striations, ridges throughout. The undulations and ridges get more pronounced at what has (on basis of the ridges) been considered the bottom part of the vessel (3c, 3b).